

CO2 Emission per GDP Forecast 2020-2100

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Abstract

This work includes Business As Usual (BAU) forecast of the world's global CO₂ emissions per GDP (Cp\$) in the period 2020-2100.

The CO₂ emissions BAU forecast is from the publication "*Dataset Global Warming Forecast using Acceleration Factors*" [3]. According to this publication, the CO₂ emissions without international transport will change from 33,803 MtCO₂/y in 2020 to 70,191 MtCO₂/y in 2100, a 108% increase.

The GDP forecast applies a parabolic trendline of the last 30 years. According to this calculation, the world GDP will change from 126.3 MM\$/y in 2020 to 728.1 MM\$/y in 2100, a 476% increase.

CO₂ emissions per GDP (Cp\$) are calculated by dividing the CO₂ emissions per year by the GDP in the same year.

According to the forecast, the world 0.000268 tCO₂/\$GDP Cp\$ in 2020 will decrease by 64% in 2100 to 0.000096 tCO₂/\$GDP.

Keywords: Climate Change, Global Warming, CO₂ emissions, CO₂ emissions forecast, CO₂ emissions per GDP

Glossary

\$\$GDP	\$GDP of cumulative GDP in a period
\$GDP	constant international \$(2017) of Gross Domestic Product
\$GDP/y,cap	\$GDP per year per capita
Ave	average
BAU	Business As Usual
CCO2	cumulative emissions of CO2 in a period
CCO2/\$\$GDP	cumulative emissions of CO2 in a period per cumulative GDP in the same period
CCp\$\$	cumulative emissions of CO2 in a period per cumulative GDP in the same period, CCO2/\$\$GDP
CO2	emissions of Carbon Dioxide, CO2
Cp\$	CO2 emissions per GDP, tCO2/y,\$ (ton CO2 per year, per \$2017)
GDP	Gross Domestic Product, constant international \$(2017)
Global Warming	global surface temperature above the 1850-1900 baseline, land+ocean, °C
MM\$	10 ¹² \$, 10 ^{^12} \$, 1,000,000,000,000 \$
MtCO2/y	Mega-ton CO2 per year, 10 ⁶ ton, 10 ^{^6} ton, 1,000,000 ton CO2 per year
OWID	Our World in Data – Internet site [1] [2]
Ref	reference
tCCO2	ton of cumulative CO2 in period
tCCO2/\$\$GDP	ton of cumulative CO2 in period per cumulative \$GDP of GDP in the same period
tCO2	ton CO2
tCO2/\$GDP	ton CO2 per \$GDP

Sources of Data

CO2 emissions and population datasets are from OWID [1] [2] “CO2 emissions produced from fossil fuels and cement production only – land use change is not included”.

World and international transport cumulative CO2 emissions above the 1875 baseline are from the publications [4] [5] [6] based on [1] [2].

GDP dataset is from World Bank (WB) [3] “GDP, PPP (constant 2017 international \$)”.

Part of the missing GDP data for 1990+ in the World Bank dataset [3] was calculated using OWID [1] [2] and conversion factors between the datasets for each year based on conversion factors between the datasets for the USA.

Dataset

Table 1 - [Dataset \[1\] \[2\] \[3\] \[4\] \[5\] \[6\]](#)

	CO2 emissions	Population	GDP
Source of data	OWID	OWID	World Bank
Reference	[1] [2]	[1] [2]	[8]
From year	1750	1800	1990
To year	2020	2020	2020
CO2 from fossil fuels	Yes		
CO2 from cement production	Yes		
CO2 from other sources	No		
Other GHG	No		
Land use change	No		
Units	MtCO2/y		Constant International \$ 2017
Resolution	1 tCO2/y	1 Resident	1 Constant International \$ 2017

The publication “*Dataset Global Warming Forecast using Acceleration Factors*” [6] includes Global Warming and CO2 emissions time series for 2020-2100.

Business As Usual Scenario

All calculations and estimations in this work are for the Business As Usual (BAU) scenario, the effectiveness of the future CO2 emissions mitigation will be as in the past.

CO2 Emissions

Chart 1 - Global CO2 emissions per year without international transport 1990-2020
[tCO2/y] [1] [2]

Chart 2 - CO2 emissions per year without international transport BAU forecast 2020-2100 [MtCO2/y] [6]

The dataset of CO2 emissions forecast for 2020-2100 is available in the publication [6].

World Population Forecast

The population forecast for the period 2020-2100 is based on the Excel chart parabolic trendline formula of the actual world population in the period 1990-2020 [1] [2].

Chart 3 - World population parabolic trendlines formula 1990-2020 [1] [2]

Table 2 - World population parabolic trendlines formula 1990-2020 [1] [2]

$$y = 97038.960947752000x^2 + 78816017.124269500000x + 5261771158.068770000000$$

a	97039.0
b	78816017.1
c	5261771158.1
start	1989

Table 3 - World population forecast

World population 1990	5,327,529,078
World population 2020	7,794,798,725
Parabolic trendline chart formula:	
$y = 97038.960947752x^2 + 78816017.1242695x + 5261771158.06877$	
World population 2020 according to the formula	7,798,322,130
Δ to actual	0.045%
World population 2100	15,205,966,097

Chart 4 - World population forecast 2020-2100

The dataset of population forecast for 2020-2100 is available in the publication [7].

GDP Forecast

The world GDP forecast for the period 2020-2100 is based on the Excel chart parabolic trendline formula of actual world GDP in the period 1990-2020 [3].

Chart 5 - World GDP parabolic trendlines formula 1990-2020 [3]

Table 4 - World GDP parabolic trendlines formula 1990-2020 [3]

$$y = 42206450113.7832x^2 + 1446788661576.16x + 47507310117185$$

a	42206450113.8
b	1446788661576.2
c	47507310117185.0
start	1989

Table 5 - World GDP forecast

World GDP 1990	51,241,010,872,505	\$GDP
World GDP 2020	126,318,951,010,345	\$GDP
Parabolic trendline chart formula:		
$y = 42206450113.7832x^2 + 1446788661576.16x + 47507310117185$		
World GDP 2020 according to the formula	132,918,157,185,392	\$GDP
Δ to actual	5.2%	
World GDP 2100	728,126,523,404,062	\$GDP

Chart 6 - World GDP/y forecast 2020-2100

The dataset of the world GDP forecast for 2020-2100 is available in the publication [7].

GDP per Capita

GDP per Capita is calculated by dividing the GDP per year by the population in the same year.

Table 6 - GDP per capita forecast

		1990	2020	2100
GDP	\$GDP/y	51,241,010,872,505	126,318,951,010,345	728,126,523,404,062
World population		5,327,529,078	7,794,798,725	15,205,966,097
CO2 emissions per capita	\$GDP/y,cap	9,618	16,206	47,884

Chart 7 - GDP per capita 1990-2020 [\$GDP/y.cap]

Chart 8 - GDP per capita 2020-2100 [\$GDP/y.cap]

The dataset of the world GDP per Capita forecast for 2020-2100 is available in the publication [7].

CO2 Emissions per GDP forecast

CO2 Emissions per GDP are calculated by dividing the CO2 emissions without international transport per year, by GDP in the same year.

Table 7 - CO2 emissions per GDP forecast

		1990	2020	2100
CO2 emissions per year without international transport	tCO2/y	22,191,664,636	33,803,026,586	70,191,421,088
World GDP	\$GDP/y	51,241,010,872,505	126,318,951,010,345	728,126,523,404,062
CO2 emissions per GDP	tCO2/\$GDP	0.000433	0.000268	0.000096

Chart 9 - CO2 emissions per GDP 1990-2020 [tCO2/\$GDP]

Chart 10 - CO2 emissions per GDP 2020-2100 [tCO2/\$GDP]

The dataset of CO2 emissions per GDP forecast for 2020-2100 is available in the publication [7].

Cumulative CO2 Emissions per Cumulative GDP forecast

Cumulative CO2 Emissions per Cumulative GDP are calculated by dividing the cumulative CO2 emissions without international transport per year, by the cumulative GDP in the same period.

Table 8 - Cumulative CO2 emissions per cumulative GDP

		1990-2020	2020-2100	1990-2100
Cumulative CO2 emissions without international transport	tCCO2	883,453,205,442	4,092,620,478,853	4,976,073,684,295
Cumulative GDP	\$\$GDP	2,629,956,174,159,650	31,549,705,714,587,700	34,179,661,888,747,400
Cumulative CO2 per cumulative GDP	tCCO2/\$\$GDP	0.000336	0.000130	0.000146

Chart 11 - Cumulative CO2 emissions per cumulative GDP 1990-2020
[tCCO2/\$\$GDP] BL1989

Chart 12 - Cumulative CO2 emissions per cumulative GDP 2020-2100
[tCCO2/\$\$GDP] BL2019

Chart 13 - Cumulative CO2 emissions per cumulative GDP 1990-2100
[tCCO2/\$\$GDP] BL1989

The dataset of the cumulative CO2 emissions per cumulative GDP (tCCO2/\$\$GDP) forecast for 2020-2100 is available in the publication [7].

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